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TMEM63A, a protein with lysosomal mechanosensory function, is activated in response to ERBB2 growth factor inhibition and is associated with resistance to trastuzumab.

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We identified using mRNA expression screening TMEM63A as a gene product contributing to resistance to HER2 inhibition.

Citations

Li, K., Guo, Y., Wang, Y., Zhu, R., Chen, W., Cheng, T., Zhang, X., Jia, Y., Liu, T., Zhang, W. and Jan, L.Y., 2024. Drosophila TMEM63 and mouse TMEM63A are lysosomal mechanosensory ion channels. Nature cell biology, 26(3), pp.393-403.